

ASSESSMENT OF THE PERFORMANCE OF FRESHMEN STUDENTS IN MATHEMATICS IN THE MODERN WORLD: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics in the Modern World constitutes a fundamental component of the general education curriculum for undergraduates across various disciplines. Despite its significance, numerous students experience apprehension and difficulty with the subject, as highlighted in prior research. This study investigates the performance of first-year students enrolled in Mathematics in the Modern World at Gordon College, Philippines, during the first semester of the 2023 academic year. With a total of 765 respondents from diverse academic backgrounds, the research aims to identify areas of weakness and propose interventions to enhance student learning outcomes. Through a quantitative research approach employing a non-experimental cross-sectional design, data were gathered via a survey distributed to all freshmen enrolled in the course. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were conducted to examine performance variations based on demographic profiles and to identify factors influencing student achievement. Findings reveal significant differences in performance based on demographic factors, emphasizing the need for tailored interventions. Multiple regression analysis showed that the identified factors affecting performance is program and course, which is in parallel to the difference test signifying difference in performance when grouped according to profile variables. Recommendations include faculty consultation, peer tutoring programs, syllabus revision, and alignment of teaching strategies with students' program-specific needs. Also, it is recommended that faculty share best practices among one another and have a discussion from time to time regarding methods of teaching, assessment, and classroom management. These insights offer valuable guidance for instructors and educational institutions to optimize the teaching and learning experience in Mathematics in the

Modern World, ultimately fostering improved student outcomes and alleviating anxiety associated with the subject.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Commission on Higher Education, Difficult subject, Mathematics in the Modern World, Outcome Based Teaching Learning Plan*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics in the Modern World is one of the general education courses that make up the portion of the curriculum that all undergraduates ought to take regardless of their major. According to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) memorandum series of 2013, General Education subjects exposes students to various domains of knowledge and ways of comprehending social and natural realities, developing in the process: (1) Intellectual competencies such as critical, analytical and creative thinking, and multiple forms of expression; and (2) Civic capacities demanded of membership in the community, country and world. General Education introduces students to diverse realms of knowledge and different approaches to both social and natural phenomena.

From the study of Labo (2023), stated that the CMO 20, Series of 2013 of the Commission of Higher Education recommended that Mathematics in the Modern World includes key concepts of mathematics in our world, mathematical language and symbols, problem solving and reasoning, data management, geometric design, linear programming, the mathematics of finance, apportionment and voting, logic, the mathematics of graphs, and mathematical system.

Langoban (2020) mentioned that Mathematics subject has been dreaded by most students and this is observable in the class where teachers experience the saddest reality in which the subject is deemed to be difficult for most students.

The first-year students in Gordon College who are taking Mathematics in the Modern World would find the subject as difficult and one of the reasons of having negative connotation about the subject that affects their performance is that on their perspective it is the difficult subject from their personal experiences. From the required curriculum of Commission in Higher Education for Mathematics in the Modern World during midterm the topics discussed are concepts of mathematics in our world, mathematical language and symbols, problem solving and reasoning and for final term topics depends on the different programs where the students are under, but it is usually, data management and the mathematics of finance for business and accountancy and hospitality and tourism and education.

There are 765 students were the respondents of this study from the College of Education, Arts and Sciences, College of Business and Accountancy and College of Hospitality, Tourism and Management who took the subject Mathematics in the Modern World during the first semester of the school year 2023 from Gordon College in the Philippines.

From the study of Langoban (2020) cited that from the research entitled “College Students’ Difficulties with Basic Mathematics” by Arenillo and Cruzado (2014), the subject Mathematics itself evokes fear and anxiety to college students and the difficulty experienced by most students are not just spoken in order to be heard but evidences on performance of students in Mathematics along with other disciplines are lower across various class sizes (Arenillo & Arenillo, 2013). This suggests that mathematics is a challenging topic for children, and numerous studies have been conducted to solve this issue.

To resolve the issue of difficulty experienced by most of the students, the research of this study investigates student performances enrolled in Mathematics in the Modern World. Through the student performances in Mathematics in the Modern World this study could provide valuable insights to areas where they are lacking thus allowing Gordon College instructors of Mathematics in the Modern World to adjust the Outcome Based Teaching and Learning Plan (OBTL) and its goals, implement additional interventions and revisit the effectivity of their teaching strategies.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to investigate student performances enrolled in Mathematics in the Modern World. Identify possible differences in the performance of the students, based on their demographic profiles. The feedback from the students is for improvement of the teaching Mathematics in the Modern World. To attain this objective, the following questions were raised:

1. What is the profile of the student-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex;
 - 1.2. Course;
 - 1.3. College;
 - 1.4. Instructor?
2. What is the performance of the students during the midterm and final term?
3. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the student-respondents when grouped according to profile?
4. Does the profile variables significantly affect the performance in Mathematics in the Modern World?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research approach particularly non-experimental cross-sectional design, to systematically gather numerical data regarding the performance of freshmen students in mathematics. Utilizing the survey method, data will be collected from all freshmen students enrolled in Mathematics in the Modern World in the current academic semester. A census approach will be adopted for sampling,

ensuring the inclusion of all eligible participants without any sampling. This method guarantees that the findings accurately represent the entire population of interest, ABS (2024). The data collection instrument is consisting of a structured questionnaire designed to identify the profile and grades of the students. The survey questionnaire was distributed to all freshmen students enrolled in MMW during a designated class session, accompanied by clear instructions regarding the purpose of the study, voluntary participation, confidentiality of responses, and the importance of providing honest and accurate information. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics such as mean and frequency distributions to summarize the collected data, along with inferential statistical techniques like regression analysis to examine relationships between different variables and identify factors influencing students' performance in mathematics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results, findings and discussions are logically arranged in this section based on the statement of the problem.

Profile of the student-respondents

Table 1
Profile of the Student-Respondents (N=765)

	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Female	510	66.7
Male	255	33.3
Program		
Bachelor of Arts in Communication	2	.3
Bachelor in Culture and Arts Education	3	.4
Bachelor of Elementary Education	7	.9
Bachelor of Physical Education	1	.1
Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English	7	.9
Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Filipino	8	1.0
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	63	8.2
BSBA major in Financial Management	175	22.9
BSBA major in Human Resource Management	114	14.9
BSBA major in Marketing Management	86	11.2
Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration	206	26.9
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	93	12.2
College		
College of Education, Arts, and Sciences	28	3.7

College of Business and Accountancy	644	84.2
College of Hospitality and Tourism Management	93	12.2
Instructor		
Instructor A	118	15.4
Instructor B	251	32.8
Instructor C	396	51.8

The profile of student-respondents, as depicted in Table 1, encompasses various demographic and academic characteristics. Among the 765 respondents, females dominate, constituting 66.7% of the total, while males account for 33.3%. In terms of academic programs, Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration stands out with the highest frequency at 26.9%, while Bachelor of Arts in Communication, Bachelor of Physical Education, and Bachelor in Culture and Arts Education exhibit the lowest frequencies, each representing less than 1% of the total. Regarding colleges, the College of Business and Accountancy boasts the highest representation at 84.2%, contrasting with the College of Education, Arts, and Sciences, which has the lowest at 3.7%. Instructor C has the highest frequency among instructors at 51.8%, whereas Instructor A holds the lowest frequency at 15.4%. These demographics set the stage for understanding performance in mathematics among the respondents.

The profile of student-respondents in terms of sex and enrolled academic programs with respect to the assessment of the performance of freshmen students in mathematics in the modern world varies. Laranang (2020) found that junior high school students had a moderately high level of self-confidence and enjoyment in mathematics, with attitudes significantly correlated to self-efficacy and performance. Etcuban (2019) reported positive attitudes towards the value of mathematics, but a neutral attitude towards self-confidence, enjoyment, and motivation. Keller (2020) discovered that male students were overrepresented among top-performing math students, with stronger math self-efficacy and mathematics-oriented achievement profiles. Manalaysay (2019) found no significant difference in mathematical achievement between male and female students, with mathematics anxiety being a predictor of achievement. These studies highlight the complex interplay of attitudes, self-efficacy, and gender differences in mathematics performance.

Performance of the Student-Respondents

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Performance of the Student-respondents in MMW

Grades	Midterm Grade		Final Grade	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
95 - 100	17	2.2	22	2.9
90 - 94	28	3.7	45	5.9
85 - 89	110	14.4	146	19.1
80 - 84	228	29.8	237	31.0
75 - 79	182	23.8	190	24.8
Below 75	198	25.9	92	12.0
Incomplete	0	0	5	.7
Failure Due Absences (FDA)	0	0	24	3.1
Officially Dropped	2	.3	4	.5

Table 2 provides an overview of the performance distribution of student-respondents in their Midterm and Final grades for Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW). Grades are categorized into various ranges, with frequencies and percentages indicated for each range. Notably, the most common Midterm and Final grades fall within the 80-84 range, comprising 29.8% and 31.0% respectively. Conversely, the lowest frequencies are found in the 95-100 range for Midterm grades and in the Below 75 range for Final grades.

The study of Pecjo (2022) investigates the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the academic performance in mathematics of students at Tugatog National High School in the City Division of Malabon. The findings of the study reveal that the shift to virtual/online learning during the pandemic posed significant challenges to students' learning of mathematics. This aligns with the observations in Table 2, which showed varying performance distributions among student-respondents in their Midterm and Final grades for Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW). Possible reasons for the observed performance disparities, as indicated by Pecjo's study, could include factors such as poor internet connection or access, inadequate study habits, and the challenges associated with distance learning. These factors may have contributed to difficulties in engaging with mathematics content and accessing necessary resources, ultimately impacting students' academic performance. By considering the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic on mathematics education, educators and policymakers can develop strategies to address the challenges faced by students and support their learning needs during remote learning environments.

The study by Tyaningsih et al. (2021) explores the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mathematics learning in higher education, particularly during the period of

learning from home (LFH). The findings of the study provide insights into students' perspectives on online mathematics education and its sustainability in the transition towards a new normal. The challenges identified in Tyaningsih et al.'s study, such as network constraints, health issues, and course-related difficulties during LFH, may have contributed to the observed disparities in academic performance among students. As the COVID-19 pandemic continues to shape educational practices, understanding students' experiences and addressing the challenges they face in remote learning environments are essential for supporting mathematics education and improving academic outcomes.

Difference Test

Table 3.1

Difference Test on Academic Performance grouped according to Sex

Grades	Sex	Median	Mann-Whitney U	Sig.	Remarks
Midterm	Female	80	57497.50	.013	Significant
	Male	78			
Final	Female	82	51541.00	.009	Significant
	Male	81			

Table 3.1 shows the Mann-Whitney U test on the difference in academic performance grouped according to sex. The midterm performance of the female group had higher values ($Mdn = 80$) as the performance of the Male group ($Mdn = 78$). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that this difference was statistically significant, $U = 57497.50, p = 0.013$. Similarly, the final term performance of the female group had higher values ($Mdn = 82$) as the performance of the Male group ($Mdn = 81$). A Mann-Whitney U-Test showed that this difference was statistically significant, $U = 51541.00, p = 0.009$.

The study by Perez, et al. (2021) investigates the longitudinal trend of the gender gap in mathematics achievement in Chile. Despite global efforts to address gender disparities in math performance, male students continue to outperform female students in many countries, including Chile. Using nationally representative longitudinal data and multigroup latent growth modelling (LGM), the study tracks the mathematics scoring gap from kindergarten to grade 12. The findings reveal that gender differences in mathematics performance emerge during preschool and widen as students' progress through school. Although the gap slightly decreases between grades 10 and 12, it nearly doubles by the end of high school. This widening gap has significant implications for access to higher education and the choice of major. This is relevant to the current study as it provides insights into the gender differences in mathematics performance over time. By understanding the longitudinal trends of the gender gap in mathematics achievement, educators and policymakers can develop targeted interventions to address disparities and support equitable learning opportunities for all students.

Table 3.2*Difference Test on Academic Performance grouped according to Program*

Grades	Program	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	Sig.	Remarks
Midterm	Bachelor of Arts in Communication	147.00	145.515	.000	Significant
	Bachelor in Culture and Arts Education	169.17			
	Bachelor of Elementary Education	512.21			
	Bachelor of Physical Education	106.50			
	Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English	436.36			
	Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Filipino	427.44			
	Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	628.94			
	BSBA major in Financial Management	407.41			
	BSBA major in Human Resource Management	319.25			
	BSBA major in Marketing Management	334.74			
	Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration	300.36			
	Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	467.21			
	Final	Bachelor of Arts in Communication			
Bachelor in Culture and Arts Education		112.50			
Bachelor of Elementary Education		449.71			
Bachelor of Physical Education		119.50			
Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English		296.36			
Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Filipino		254.69			
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy		606.77			
BSBA major in Financial Management		383.41			

BSBA major in Human Resource Management	281.90
BSBA major in Marketing Management	350.02
Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration	318.26
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	416.38

Note: $df = 11$

Table 3.2 presents the results of a difference test on academic performance grouped according to program, focusing on Midterm and Final grades. Regarding Midterm grades, the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy program achieves the highest mean rank of 628.94, while the Bachelor of Physical Education program obtains the lowest mean rank of 106.50. This suggests significant variation in Midterm performance across programs, as supported by a significant Kruskal-Wallis H statistic ($\chi^2(11) = 145.515, p = .000$). Similarly, for Final grades, the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy program achieves the highest mean rank of 606.77, while the Bachelor of Physical Education program again obtains the lowest mean rank of 119.50. The Kruskal-Wallis H statistic remains significant ($\chi^2(11) = 128.651, p = .000$), indicating notable differences in Final performance among programs. Overall, the results suggest significant disparities in academic performance across different academic programs, highlighting the need for further investigation into the factors influencing these differences.

The study by Tan and Dejoras (2019) investigates the problem-solving ability of graduates from Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and non-STEM backgrounds enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Mathematics Education (BS MathEd) program. Utilizing a Mathematics Problem Solving Ability Test developed by the researchers, the study finds no significant difference in problem-solving ability between STEM and non-STEM graduates. Both groups were identified as apprentice problem-solvers, capable of obtaining partially correct solutions but not consistently arriving at the correct answers. The findings suggest the need for enhancements in the basic education program, particularly in the successful implementation of K to 12. Recommendations include providing quality instructional materials, conducting teacher training programs, and considering teachers' qualifications in hiring. Additionally, the study suggests that the BS Mathematics Education Program should not exclusively admit STEM graduates and proposes remedial activities to improve problem-solving abilities among pre-service mathematics teachers. The differences in academic performance among students from various academic backgrounds, specifically in the context of mathematics education programs. Both studies contribute to understanding the factors influencing students' performance within specific academic programs and highlight the importance of addressing skill gaps to enhance educational outcomes.

The article by Yousuf Al Husaini and Nur Syufiza Ahmad Shukor (2022) explores the factors affecting students' academic performance, with a focus on assessing students'

standing within a university. The study emphasizes the importance of evaluating students' performance across various courses throughout a semester to aid academic staff, administrators, and decision-makers in making informed assessments and supporting students' academic progress. The authors highlight the rising challenges of delayed graduation and college dropouts in Oman, underscoring the impact on higher education missions. By conducting a systematic literature review, the study identifies several key factors influencing academic performance, including entry grades, family support, accommodation, student gender, previous assessment grades, GPA, and e-learning activity. These findings provide valuable insights for researchers and educators interested in understanding and addressing issues related to academic performance, such as developing predictive models. It aligns with the exploration of factors influencing academic performance, albeit from a broader perspective. Both studies contribute to understanding the multifaceted nature of academic achievement and the importance of identifying and addressing factors that impact students' success in education.

Table 3.3

Difference Test on Academic Performance grouped according to College

Grades	College	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	Sig.	Remarks
Midterm	College of Education, Arts, and Sciences	391.70	16.142	.000	Significant
	College of Business and Accountancy	369.23			
	College of Hospitality and Tourism Management	467.21			
Final	College of Education, Arts, and Sciences	280.41	10.024	.007	Significant
	College of Business and Accountancy	362.85			
	College of Hospitality and Tourism Management	416.38			

Note: $df = 2$

Table 3.3 shows the difference test on the performance of the student-respondents grouped according to different colleges. A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that there was a statistically significant difference in midterm performance among the different colleges, $\chi^2(2) = 16.142, p = .000$, with mean rank grade of 467.21 for College of Hospitality and Tourism Management which is greater than mean rank grade of 369.23 for the College of Business and Accountancy. Similarly, there was a statistically significant difference in final term performance among the different colleges, $\chi^2(2) = 10.024, p = .007$, with mean rank grade score of 416.38 for College of Hospitality and Tourism Management.

Hospitality and Tourism Management which is greater than mean rank grade score of 280.41 for the College of Education, Arts, and Sciences.

Choosing college courses with respect to performance in mathematics is an important consideration for students. Research suggests that different math pathways can have varying effects on student outcomes. One study found that while the Liberal Arts math pathway may increase the likelihood of students passing the first gateway course, Algebra pathways tend to result in greater longer-term coursetaking success (Mokher & Hu, 2022). Another study indicates that offering a choice of instructional methods, such as differentiated instruction, can benefit groups underrepresented in mathematics and improve student achievement in college-level math courses (Roop et al., 2018). Redesigning math classes using modern technology, such as a lab-based adaptive model, has also been shown to increase pass rates and decrease withdrawal rates (Stefanov & Griffiths, 2023). Additionally, providing a basic mathematics course alongside algebra classes can have a positive impact on student performance, particularly for those with low math proficiency (Villanueva-Cantillo et al., 2020). Strengthening students' regular performance and process management is also important for improving final performance in math courses.

Table 3.4
Difference Test on Academic Performance grouped according to Instructor

Grades	College	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	Sig.	Remarks
Midterm	Instructor A	455.38	34.392	.000	Significant
	Instructor B	415.78			
	Instructor C	338.50			
Final	Instructor A	389.60	11.164	.004	Significant
	Instructor B	395.97			
	Instructor C	341.75			

Note: $df = 2$

Table 3.4 shows the difference test on the performance of the student-respondents grouped according to different instructors. A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that there was a statistically significant difference in midterm performance among the different colleges, $\chi^2(2) = 34.392, p = .000$, with mean rank grade of 455.38 for Instructor A which is greater than mean rank grade of 338.50 of Instructor C. Similarly, there was a statistically significant difference in final term performance among the instructors, $\chi^2(2) = 11.164, p =$

.004, with mean rank grade score of 395.97 of instructor B which is greater than mean rank grade score of 341.75 of instructor C.

Research has shown that teachers' evaluations of students' mathematical ability can be influenced by biases, particularly against Black, Hispanic, and female students (Copur-Gencturk, 2019). However, the relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and instructional quality in mathematics education is also crucial, with higher self-efficacy beliefs and coursework in mathematics being associated with better student achievement (Toropova, 2019). Furthermore, students' perceptions of their mathematics teachers' professional competence can have a significant impact on their engagement, achievement, and choice of college major (Shin, 2021). Therefore, when choosing college instructors for mathematics, it is important to consider not only their expertise in the subject but also their ability to mitigate biases and create an inclusive learning environment.

Regression Analysis

Table 4.1

Regression Coefficients for Predicting Midterm Performance in MMW by Profile Variables

Variable	B	t	p	Remarks
(Constant)	82.188	37.272	.000	Significant
Sex at Birth	-.724	-1.323	.186	Not Significant
Program	-1.555	-7.959	.000	Significant
College	6.507	6.213	.000	Significant
Faculty	-.528	-1.309	.191	Not Significant

Note: $R = 0.329$, $R_{adj}^2 = 0.104$ ($F(4, 758) = 22.997$, $p = 0.00$)

A multiple regression was run to predict the performance in MMW from sex, program, college, and instructor. These variables statistically significantly predict midterm performance, $F(4, 758) = 22.997$, $p = 0.000$. Although the quality of prediction of the profiles to the midterm performance which is 32.9% is low, and the proportion of variance of the midterm performance that can be explained by the profile is 10.4%. The general form of the equation to predict midterm performance from sex, program, college, and instructor is: $Predicted\ MT = 82.188 - 0.724(sex) - 1.555(program) + 6.507(college) - 0.528(Faculty)$. The coefficient indicates that only the program and the college can predict the midterm performance of the student-respondents, $p < 0.05$.

Research on gender differences in mathematics performance has yielded mixed results. Reilly (2019) found small to medium-sized gender differences in mathematics achievement, with boys reporting more favorable attitudes and girls reporting lower self-efficacy beliefs. However, Copur-Gencturk (2019) revealed biases against female, Black, and Hispanic students in teachers' evaluations of mathematical ability. O'Connell (2018)

emphasized the role of student ability and past performance in predicting success in mathematics courses, while Bada (2018) found a low positive correlation between gender and academic achievement in mathematics and science. These studies suggest that while gender, course, and professor choice may play a role in predicting midterm performance in mathematics, they are not the only factors at play.

Table 4.2
Regression Coefficients for Predicting Final Term Performance in MMW by Profile Variables

Variable	B	t	p	Remarks
(Constant)	80.843	38.299	.000	Significant
Sex at Birth	-1.069	-5.671	.000	Not Significant
Program	5.183	5.162	.000	Significant
College	-.808	-1.511	.131	Significant
Faculty	.163	.424	.672	Not Significant

Note: $R = 0.241$, $R_{adj}^2 = 0.053$ ($F(4, 727) = 11.196$, $p = 0.00$)

Multiple regression was run to predict the performance in MMW from sex, program, college, and instructor. These variables statistically significantly predict final performance, $F(4, 727) = 11.196$, $p = 0.000$. Although the quality of prediction of the profiles to the finals performance which is 24.1% is low, and the proportion of variance of the final performance that can be explained by the profile is 5.3%. The general form of the equation to predict midterm performance from sex, program, college, and instructor is: $Predicted\ FG = 80.843 - 1.069(sex) + 5.183(program) - 9.808(college) - 0.163(Faculty)$. The coefficient indicates that only the program and the college can predict the midterm performance of the student-respondents, $p < 0.05$.

Regression coefficients for predicting final term performance in mathematics by student's gender, course, and chosen professor were examined in multiple studies. Hurdle et al. (2022) found that course times, gender, major, instructor, and term were significant variables in performance, with time having a significant impact. Zogheib et al. (2014) discovered that student gender was the most significant predictor of performance, with female students outperforming male students. Hasanah et al. (2022) used linear regression to predict academic performance in mathematics and found that the failure variable had a positive effect on performance. Morales-Jiménez (2022) proposed a regression-based early prediction system for student achievement, which showed promising results in predicting final scores. Overall, these studies highlight the importance of considering various factors, such as gender, course times, and instructor, in predicting mathematics performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The typical respondent of the study was female, taking Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration under the College of Business and Accountancy and was taught by Instructor B.
2. The average midterm performance of the student-respondents was 78.86 which is low average and the average final performance 80.91 which is average. This performance is way low for a college student.
3. There is a significant difference on the performance of the student-respondents when grouped according to profile, specifically:
 - 3.1. female performed better than male both for the midterm and final term;
 - 3.2. elementary education students performed better than physical education students on midterm and accountancy students performed better than communication arts students for final term;
 - 3.3. students under hospitality and tourism management performed better than accountancy students during the midterm while hospitality and tourism students performed better than education and arts students;
 - 3.4. students under instructor A performed better than students under instructor C during the midterm, while student under instructor B performed better than students under instructor C on final term.
4. Profile variables have statistically significant effect on grades of the student-respondents. Particularly, the course program and what college the students are in have significant effect on the performance in Mathematics in the Modern World.

Recommendations

1. Faculty must use consultation time to help the challenged students.
2. The Math and Physics Department must foster a peer tutoring program in collaboration with the BSED Mathematics Students and Gordon College Tribo ng Math (GCTM). This may be of great help for the challenged students.
3. Revisit the distribution of the topics in the syllabus for mid and final terms. There are 199 or 26.01% who failed during the midterm. While there are 92 or 12.02% during the final term.
4. Revisit and revise the strategies in handling different programs base on the OBTL syllabus. The course is general in context but must be applied to the specific program of the students particularly in giving activities and sample problems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were include obtaining prior informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality of responses, and addressing potential limitations such as reliance on self-reported data and possible response biases. All participants can withdraw from or exit the research at any time without feeling obligated. The participants are not

required to give a reason for leaving the research. It is critical to emphasize to participants that there will be no negative consequences or ramifications for refusing to engage. After all, they are spending the time to assist with study, so they should appreciate their judgments without attempting to modify them.

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